

solid mass separated after 24 hrs. The solid was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol; yield-about 60-70%. The relevant data are given in Table 1.

5-Nitro-4(2)-[4-oxo-6,8-disubstituted-3H-quinazolin-3-yl]-benzylidene malonylureas(V) :

A mixture of (IV) (0.01 mole) urea (0.01 mole) and ethanolic NaOEt (0.01 mole) was refluxed for 6-7 hrs on a steam bath and subsequently refluxed on oil bath for 16 hrs at 110-115°. The mixture then treated with 20 ml in hot dil. HCl and was kept in an ice-chest overnight. The solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethyl alcohol. The yield was about 60-70%. The relevant data are given in Table 1.

Antibacterial screening : All the compounds (V) were screened out for their antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, using the method of Verma and Nobels^{1,2}. Zone of inhibition to these bacteria ranged between 5-15 mm for compounds Va, Vd, Ve, Vg and Vh. Compounds Vb, Vc and Vf were inactive. Compound Ve was found to be the best active (15 mm sterilization zone).

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Synthesis and CNS Activity of 1-(5'-Alkyl, 1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl), 2-methyl, 4-arylidene-imidazol-5-ones.

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FIFTEEN new thiadiazolyl imidazolone derivatives (III) have been synthesised by the condensation of some 2-methyl, 4-arylidene azalactones (I) with 2-amino, 5-alkyl-thiadiazoles (II) in pyridine. The 2-amino - thiadiazole¹⁻⁵ and imidazolone⁶⁻⁸ derivatives have been reported to possess various CNS activities. It was thought worthwhile to investigate whether the compounds having both imidazolone and thiadiazole moieties can have better pharmacological results. The reported MAO-inhibitory activity in imidazolone nucleus^{9,10}, guided the idea that the mechanism of action of the aforesaid compounds on parkinsonian features could be dopaminergic, therefore their MAO-inhibitory activity was also tested.

2-Amino, 5-alkyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazoles : These were synthesised by the method of Funatsukuri *et al*¹¹.

2-Methyl, 4-arylidene-azlact-5-ones : These were synthesised using the procedure of Vogel¹², Herbert and Shemin¹³, Dakin¹⁴ and Niender and Ziering¹⁵.

1-(5'-Methyl, 1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl)-2'-methyl-4-(p-methoxy benzylidene)-imidazol-5-one :

2-Amino, 5-methyl 1, 3, 4-thiadiazole (0.01 mole) and 2-methyl, 4-(p-methoxy benzylidene)-azlact-5-one (0.01 mole) were taken in pyridine (15 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for about 6 hr on a sand bath. The excess of pyridine was distilled off at reduced pressure and the residue was cooled at room temperature. It was then poured in a mixture of 50 ml conc. HCl and 50 g ice and left overnight. The solid separated was filtered and recrystallised twice with ethanol and dried. Yield 70% ; m.p. 218-19°. IR(KBr) 1660 cm⁻¹ (for C=C stretch trisubstituted); 1680cm⁻¹ (for ring N-C- group of imidazolone moiety);

1640 cm⁻¹ (for ring C=N bonding). Similarly other 1-(5'-alkyl-1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl)-2-methyl-4-arylidene imidazol-5-ones were prepared and are described in Table 1.

Pharmacology : All the compounds were screened for CNS activity on albino mice of either sex. Acute toxicity test was also done and the ALD₅₀ of these compounds was also determined following the method of Weil¹⁶. ALD₅₀ are given in Table 1.

The compounds are relatively nontoxic. Compound Nos. 5,12,13 produced piloerection and stimulations